

STUDY SKILLS OF STUDENT TEACHERS IN TAMILNADU AND KERALA

M. S. Manju* & Dr. J. V. Asha**

* Research Scholar, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamilnadu

** Assistant Professor, Department of Education, Kerala University, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala

Cite This Article: M. S. Manju & Dr. J. V. Asha, "Study Skills of Student Teachers in Tamilnadu and Kerala", *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education*, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 225-229, 2017.

Copy Right: © IJMRME, R&D Modern Research Publication, 2017 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

This study aims at finding out the differences in study skills of student teachers with respect to gender, and marital status. 1,014 student teachers, from Kanyakumari district of Tamil Nadu State and Thiruvananthapuram district of Kerala State, were selected using simple random sampling technique. The investigator used a self-made tool, with three dimensions viz. gathering information, storing information and retrieving information, for assessing the study skills of student teachers. Percentage analysis and 't' test were used to analyse the collected data. Percentage analysis reveals that majority of the student teachers have moderate level of study skills with regard to gender and marital status. 't' test reveals the following: (i) There is no significant difference in the dimensions of study skills and in total with respect to the gender; (ii) There is significant difference in the dimension of gathering information and there is no significant difference in the dimensions of storing information, retrieving information and study skills in total with regard to their marital status.

Key Words: Study Skills, Student Teachers & Secondary Level

Introduction:

A skill is a learned activity that can be developed through practice and reflection. Certain skills are needed for success in academic life for the close study or examination of a subject. Study skills, study habits, learning styles, meta-learning skills etc. are major factors that help students to attain their desired goals. Those students with weak study skills stumble year after year, requiring special help, remedial measures, individual tutoring and developing of themselves negative images as students (Glanz, 2004). Learning to learn is one of the main purposes of teaching, training and learning. Efficient learning process does not depend on teaching alone; it depends on learning procedures and learning techniques as well. Study skills are a major factor that helps students to attain goal. Fine tuning a skill involves developing personal qualities as well, such as awareness, commitment, determination, perseverance, self-motivation, time-management, positive thinking etc. (Cottrell, 2003). For this process one should possess certain skills known as 'study skills'.

Significance of the Study:

Study skills help to organize study environment, generate and maintain motivation, create positive attitude towards learning goals and tasks, make new information more meaningful and integrate new information with old knowledge (Hussain, 2006). Study skills are strategies and methods of purposeful learning usually centred on reading and writing. Study skills include those competencies associated in acquiring, recording, organizing, synthesizing, remembering and using information in future. Hurley (1994) describes study skills as key skills for all areas of education, including advanced study. Effective study skills are essential for trainees to acquire good achievements and are useful in general to improve learning throughout one's life in support of career and other interest (Ehrman, 1998). The acquisition, integration, organization and storage of new knowledge are facilitated by the use of effective and efficient learning strategies which include the above mentioned study skills. Different study skills are essential for academic success. The most common study skills include organization, time management, research skills, note making, note taking, reference skills, effective listening, and reading information transfer etc. Study skills are pre-requisite for educational success. Students with effective study skills have been shown to overcome educational failure and improve their physical and mental health.

National development depends on the quality of teachers. For delivery of quality education, we need quality teachers who are committed to teaching profession and equipped with definite skills and competencies. In order to reach the expectation as effective and quality professional, one needs to have good study skills. Hence this study intends to find out the study skills of secondary teacher trainees with respect to certain background variables.

Objectives:

- ✓ To find out the level of study skills of student teachers with respect to gender.

- ✓ To find out the level of study skills of student teachers with respect to marital status.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference between the male and the female student teachers in their study skills.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference between the married and the unmarried student teachers in their study skills.

Hypotheses:

- ✓ There is no significant difference between the male and the female student teachers in their study skills.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between the married and the unmarried student teachers in their study skills.

Methodology:

For this study, the investigator used a normative survey method. Simple random sampling was the technique used for sampling. In drawing the sample, representation was given to gender, and marital status. Thus 1014 student teachers at secondary level formed the sample of the study. The sample was drawn from Kanyakumari district of Tamil Nadu and Trivandrum district of Kerala. Necessary data for the study were collected using a self-made study skills inventory. Percentage analysis and ‘t’ test were used in the analysis of data.

Results: Objective Testing

Objective 1: To find out the level of study skills of student teachers with respect to gender.

Table 1: Level of Study Skills of Student Teachers with Respect to Gender

Study Skill Dimensions	Gender	Low		Moderate		High	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Gathering information	Male	14	20.5	39	57.4	15	22.1
	Female	234	24.7	500	52.9	212	22.4
Storing information	Male	15	22.1	39	57.3	14	20.6
	Female	209	22.1	520	55.0	217	22.9
Retrieving information	Male	16	23.5	35	51.5	17	25.0
	Female	234	24.7	486	51.4	226	23.9
Study skills in total	Male	15	22.1	38	55.8	15	22.1
	Female	223	23.6	485	51.3	238	25.1

Figure 1: Level of Study Skills of Student Teachers with Respect to Gender

It is inferred from Table 1 that 20.5% of male student teachers have low, 57.4% of them have moderate and 22.1% of them have high level of gathering information. Regarding the female student teachers, 24.7% of them have low, 52.9% of them have moderate and 22.4% of them have high level of gathering information.

22.1% of male student teachers have low, 57.3% of them have moderate and 20.6% of them have high level of storing information. Regarding the female student teachers, 22.1% of them have low, 55.0% of them have moderate and 22.9% of them have high level of storing information.

23.5% of male student teachers have low, 51.5% of them have moderate and 25.0% of them have high level of retrieving information. Regarding the female student teachers, 24.7% of them have low, 51.4% of them have moderate and 23.9% of them have high level of retrieving information.

22.1% of male student teachers have low, 55.8% of them have moderate and 22.1% of them have high level of study skills in total. Regarding the female student teachers, 23.6% of them have low, 51.3% of them have moderate and 25.1% of them have high level of study skills in total. This has been shown in the figure 1.

Objective 2: To find out the level of study skills of student teachers with respect to marital status.

Table 2: Level of Study Skills of Student Teachers with Respect to Marital Status

Dimensions	Marital Status	Low		Moderate		High	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Gathering information	Married	33	21.4	83	53.9	38	24.7
	Unmarried	215	25.0	456	53.0	189	22.0
Storing information	Married	36	23.4	88	57.1	30	19.5
	Unmarried	188	21.8	471	54.8	201	23.4
Retrieving information	Married	41	26.6	81	52.6	32	20.8
	Unmarried	209	24.3	440	51.2	211	24.5
Study skills in total	Married	38	24.7	82	53.2	34	22.1
	Unmarried	200	23.2	441	51.3	219	25.5

Figure 2: Level of Study Skills of Student Teachers with Respect to Marital Status

It is inferred from the Table 2 that 21.4% of married student teachers have low, 53.9% of them have moderate and 24.7% of them have high level of gathering information. Regarding the unmarried student teachers, 25.0% of them have low, 53.0% of them have moderate and 22.0% of them have high level of gathering information.

23.4% of married student teachers have low, 57.1% of them have moderate and 19.5% of them have high level of storing information. Regarding the unmarried student teachers, 21.8% of them have low, 54.8% of them have moderate and 23.4% of them have high level of storing information.

26.6% of married student teachers have low, 52.6% of them have moderate and 20.8% of them have high level of retrieving information. Regarding the unmarried student teachers, 24.3% of them have low, 51.2% of them have moderate and 24.5% of them have high level of retrieving information.

24.7% of married student teachers have low, 53.2% of them have moderate and 22.1% of them have high level of study skills in total. Regarding the unmarried student teachers, 23.2% of them have low, 51.3% of them have moderate and 25.5% of them have high level of study skills in total. This has been shown in the figure 2.

Hypotheses Testing:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the male and the female student teachers in their study skills.

Table 3: Difference between the Male and the Female Student Teachers in their Study Skills

Dimensions	Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	Calculated 't' value	Remarks
Gathering information	Male	68	66.13	10.628	0.36	NS
	Female	946	65.66	10.190		
Storing information	Male	68	64.04	8.683	0.56	NS
	Female	946	64.65	8.479		
Retrieving information	Male	68	65.50	10.189	0.53	NS
	Female	946	64.82	10.095		
Study skills in total	Male	68	195.68	24.711	0.23	NS
	Female	946	195.03	21.614		

(The table value of t is 1.96, NS - Not Significant)

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated t value (0.36, 0.56, 0.53, 0.23) is less than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the respective null hypothesis is accepted. Thus, the result shows that there is no significant difference between the male and the female student teachers in the dimensions of gathering information, storing information, retrieving information and study skills in total.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the married and the unmarried student teachers in their study skills.

Table 4: Table Difference between the Married and the Unmarried Student Teachers in their Study Skills

Dimensions	Marital Status	N	Mean	S.D.	Calculated 't' value	Remarks
Gathering information	Married	154	67.31	9.726	2.13	S
	Unmarried	860	65.40	10.279		
Storing information	Married	154	63.77	8.043	1.33	NS
	Unmarried	860	64.76	8.563		
Retrieving information	Married	154	64.33	9.805	0.71	NS
	Unmarried	860	64.96	10.152		
Study skills in total	Married	154	195.41	22.411	0.20	NS
	Unmarried	860	195.01	21.729		

(The table value of t is 1.96, S - Significant, NS - Not Significant)

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated t value (1.33, 0.71, and 0.20) is less than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the respective null hypothesis is accepted. Thus, the result shows that there is no significant difference between the married and the unmarried student teachers in the dimensions of storing information, retrieving information and study skills in total. But there is significant difference between the married and the unmarried student teachers in the dimension of gathering information.

While comparing the mean scores of the married (Mean=67.31) and the unmarried student teachers (Mean=65.40), the married student teachers are found to be better than the unmarried student teachers in the dimension of gathering information.

Major Findings:

- ✓ Most of the student teachers possess moderate level of study skills with respect to gender.
- ✓ Most of the student teachers possess moderate level of study skills with respect to marital status.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between the male and the female student teachers in their study skills dimensions and in total.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between the married and the unmarried student teachers in storing information, retrieving information and study skills in total; but there is significant difference in the dimension of gathering information.

Conclusion:

It is concluded from the study that there exists no significant difference in study skills with respect to gender. A good, effective study required flexibility in study speed, clear perception and memory retention, concentration, planning and evaluation. Study is a complex activity and students have to use a combination of study skills. Mastering study skills makes study more enjoyable and effective which in turn strengthen the students' interest so he/she spends more time studying (Seif, 1997). The students with educational success pointed out the study skills as a contributing factor while the students with educational failure expressed lack of good study skills a major factor of their failure.

References:

1. Cottrel, S. M. (2003). Skills for success: The personal development planning handbook. Basingstoke, New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
2. Ehrman, Madeline E. (1998). Understanding second language learning difficulties. London: Sage Publications.

3. Glanz, J. (2004). Assistant principal's handbook: Strategies for success. Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin Press.
4. Hurley, (1994) cited by Cottrell, Stella. (2001). in Teaching study skills and supporting learning. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
5. Hussain, A. (2006). Effect of guidance services on study attitudes, study habits and academic achievement of secondary school students. Bulletin of Education and Research, 28(1), 35-45.
6. Seif, A. (1997). Methods of learning and study. Tehran: Agah publication.